

THE PATHOGENESIS OF DEFICIENCY DISEASE.

No. III. THE INFLUENCE OF DIETARIES DEFICIENT IN ACCESSORY FOOD FACTORS ON THE INTESTINE.

BY

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THE pathological changes in the intestine which result from dietaries deficient in accessory food factors have been studied in:

- (1) pigeons fed exclusively on autoclaved milled rice : that is to say, on food lacking in all three classes of accessory food factors ;
- (2) pigeons fed on autoclaved rice together with fresh butter and onions : that is to say, on food deficient in accessory food factors of the ' B ' class ;
- (3) pigeons fed on autoclaved rice together with fresh butter : that is to say, on food deficient in accessory food factors of the ' C ' class (anti-scorbutic substances), as well as in factors of the ' B ' class (the so-called ' anti-neuritic vitamines ') ;
- (4) guinea-pigs fed on a diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk : that is to say, on food deficient in anti-scorbutic substances; and

- (5) guinea-pigs fed on an exclusive diet of autoclaved rice : that is to say, on food deficient in all three classes of accessory food factors.

While the morbid changes resulting from these dietaries are attributable in the main to deficiency of accessory food factors, their genesis is no doubt contributed to, or their effects enhanced, by deficiency of other essential attributes of a satisfactorily balanced ration.

All experiments were carried out under conditions and precautions previously detailed(1) : they were continued to a point at which death of the animals occurred or was about to occur.

I. THE EFFECTS OF AN AUTOCLAVED RICE DIETARY ON THE INTESTINE OF PIGEONS.

The pathological changes were studied macroscopically in 152 pigeons fed exclusively on milled or on autoclaved milled rice, and microscopically in 24. All these birds developed *polyneuritis gallinarum* in consequence of the deficient dietary.

A.—Macroscopical Appearances.

The chief macroscopical features observed at autopsy in the intestine were atrophy and congestion, both of which might be extreme. All cases presented atrophy in greater or lesser degree, while a proportion, estimated at about 30 per cent, showed no congestion appreciable by the naked eye.

The upper portion of the intestine of healthy pigeons, especially that part embracing the pancreas, is thick and muscular (Fig. 6). It is this portion which suffers most in consequence of the deficient dietary. The atrophy is of all grades of severity ; it may be comparatively slight, or progress to a point at which the intestinal walls are so thin as to be transparent. As a rule the atrophy is more marked the longer the bird is under the influence of the defective diet.

The congestion is commonly confined to the upper part of the alimentary tract ; less often it involves its whole extent. The branches of the mesenteric vessels surrounding the bowel may be greatly engorged, and extravasations of blood are occasionally to be seen under its serous coat.

The atrophy of the bowel, although often considerable, was usually less marked than in cases dying in consequence of complete 'vitaminic' starvation. Histologically one did not, as a rule, encounter the same degree of congestion: actual hæmorrhages were more rarely met with, while the degree of atrophy of the myenteron and of the elements of the mucous membrane, although usually considerable, were often comparatively slight. Two cases were encountered amongst twelve examined where bacterial infection of the bowel walls had assisted in bringing about changes as pronounced as those so commonly seen in the case of birds wholly deprived of accessory food factors.

Fresh butter and onions when added to a dietary of autoclaved rice thus provide some at least of those factors on which the functional perfection of the alimentary tract is dependent.

III. THE EFFECTS OF A DIETARY OF AUTOCLAVED RICE AND BUTTER ON THE INTESTINE OF PIGEONS.

The effects of this dietary, which is deficient in 'vitamines' of the 'B' and 'C' classes and gives rise to typical *polyneuritis*, were studied macroscopically in eighteen cases and microscopically in six.

The description given of the effects of complete 'vitaminic' starvation applies to these cases. The butter used afforded the birds no protection in so far as the intestines were concerned. Figs. 6-9 typify the appearances seen.

With the reservation that the number of birds in this category is small in comparison with those in the two previous categories, one is led to suspect that, since butter did not protect, it was the addition of fresh onions to the basal diet of autoclaved rice that afforded the birds in the second category the measure of protection against congestive and hæmorrhagic processes which they undoubtedly enjoyed.

In order to provide further evidence on this point, the appearances presented by the intestines of guinea-pigs fed on dietaries (a) of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, and (b) of autoclaved rice, were studied.

IV. THE EFFECTS OF A SCORBUTIC DIET ON THE INTESTINE OF GUINEA-PIGS.

Twelve guinea-pigs, with an equal number of controls, were employed in this experiment. The animals were isolated in separate cages. They

were fed on crushed oats and autoclaved milk. The oats were locally grown and were of poor quality. The milk was autoclaved at a temperature of 130°C. for one hour. The experiment was continued to the death of the pigs, which occurred within periods ranging from twenty to thirty days. Autopsies were performed immediately after death with the detail and precautions previously described(1). Three of twelve guinea-pigs were excluded owing to the presence of complicating pathological processes, such as peritonitis. The macroscopical appearances found in the gastro-intestinal tract were studied in nine cases; the microscopical in five.

A.—Macroscopical Appearances.

The most notable feature present was intense congestion of the duodenum. This part of the bowel, for a variable distance from the pylorus, was in four out of nine cases so congested as almost to present the appearances seen in strangulated bowel. The congested area was sharply demarcated by the pylorus and extended down the bowel for a distance of from one to two inches. In two other cases the congestion of the duodenum was of a patchy character. In the three remaining cases moderate congestion of the whole bowel was present in two, while no appreciable congestion was present in the third.

In contradistinction to the appearances presented by the upper intestine of pigeons, where the bowel is often greatly thinned, the duodenum of guinea-pigs was usually swollen and turgid, the tumefaction being due largely to hæmorrhagic infiltration of all coats of the bowel.

On opening the duodenum and examining the mucous surface with the hand-lens, ecchymoses were frequently to be seen, while areas resembling punched-out ulcers, whose base extended almost to the peritoneal coat, were occasionally encountered. At these areas the bowel walls were almost transparent.

The intestinal tract is thin in healthy guinea-pigs. Apart from the duodenum, the bowel walls in pigs dying in consequence of the deficient dietary were, generally speaking, thinner than in health. In three cases of the nine referred to, punched-out necrotic ulcers were found in the stomach. In one case as many as fifteen were counted, the base of the ulcer extending down to the peritoneal coat, the mucous membrane of the stomach being studded with the brownish debris of hæmorrhages into the interior of the organ. Thus localized, destructive changes in the

PLATE IX.

Fig. 13.

Fig. 14.

Fig. 15.

Fig. 16.

- FIG. 13. Section of duodenum of guinea-pig dying in consequence of a scorbutic diet of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, $\times 105$. Note : large degenerated and swollen ganglion (G) of myenteric plexus with a number of blood corpuscles scattered through it and through the disorganized circular layer (H) of the muscular coat. Compare with Fig. 12.
- FIG. 14. Section of upper bowel of guinea-pig, $\times 50$; showing the normal appearances in health.
- FIG. 15. Section of upper bowel of guinea-pig (No. 4) which died as a result of a crushed oats and autoclaved milk dietary, $\times 50$. Note : turgidity of bowel walls due to diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of all coats ; loss of villus-structure. Compare with Fig. 20, which is a higher magnification of a portion of this specimen.
- FIG. 16. Section of upper bowel of guinea-pig (No. 5) which died as a result of a crushed oats and autoclaved milk dietary, $\times 50$. Note : generalized atrophic and necrotic changes in the mucous membrane. The muscular coat shows some hæmorrhagic infiltration. Compare with Fig. 18, which is a higher magnification of a portion of this specimen.

mucus and underlying coats of the stomach and duodenum are amongst the more occasional results in guinea-pigs of a dietary of crushed oats and autoclaved milk.

These changes were present in the gastro-intestinal tract of guinea-pigs, dying in consequence of this dietary, which exhibited none of the characteristic naked eye appearances of scurvy. In a clinical sense then they may be regarded as pre-scorbutic.

B.—Histo-Pathology.

The microscopical appearances seen in sections of the duodenum in these cases comprised :—

- (1) turgidity, with diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of all coats of the bowel ;
- (2) degenerative changes in the myenteron ;
- (3) degenerative changes in the myenteric plexus ; and
- (4) atrophic and necrotic changes in the cellular elements of the mucous membrane.

These lesions resemble closely those described in the case of pigeons fed on an exclusive dietary of autoclaved rice. In general the same description applies to both. In the case of guinea-pigs the more diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of the mucous membrane may impart to it a degree of turgidity which is not seen in pigeons (Figs. 14 and 15). The degenerative process involves the ganglia of the myenteric plexus in a manner similar to that described in pigeons. In some cases, more especially in the vicinity of extensive hæmorrhagic infiltration of the myenteron, the normal histological structure of the ganglia may be much altered. In these circumstances, ganglia may be encountered which are infiltrated with blood, and in which no single cell contains a normal nucleus. As in the case of diseased pigeons so also in guinea-pigs, the myenteric plexus is much more prominent than in health. In hæmatoxylin-stained sections the ganglia appear swollen, the nerve cells ill-defined, the nuclei degenerated, and the nucleolus fragmented. Not all cells, however, are so affected in either species, some exhibiting nuclei of apparently normal structure. Without definitely asserting that the degenerative changes in the myenteric plexus are more pronounced in guinea-pigs than in pigeons, they certainly appear to be no less. There can be little doubt that neural lesions (Fig. 13), which may impair the nervous control of the bowel, result in consequence of

this dietary ; further histological study by special methods is necessary to determine their character.

The myenteron also is often, although not always, greatly disorganized in consequence of diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of its substance ; in such circumstances separation of muscular fibres with their segmentation and fragmentation are common appearances (Figs. 19 and 20). The degenerative and necrotic changes in the mucous membrane are as pronounced in guinea-pigs as in pigeons, and are of similar character. (compare Figs. 3, 18, 19, and 20). The same comments as to the facilities which these pathological processes afford for infection of the bowel walls and for systemic infection therefrom, apply with equal force to both species.

The histological changes in the lower bowel are of like character to those found in the upper bowel, but more moderate in degree.

The histo-pathological changes found in guinea-pigs are illustrated in the series of photo-micrographs numbered 13 to 20. If these are contrasted with Figs. 1 to 12, which illustrate the histo-pathological changes found in Aves, their similarity will become very apparent.

V. THE EFFECTS OF AN AUTOCLAVED RICE DIETARY ON THE INTESTINE OF GUINEA-PIGS.

For the purpose of this study, four guinea-pigs were employed. They were fed on an exclusive diet of autoclaved rice until death occurred, which event took place within 46 days of the initiation of the experiment.

My *post-mortem* notes with regard to the intestinal tract in these animals read as follows :—

No. 1. The duodenum shows intense congestion, the first inch-and-a-half looks almost gangrenous, so intense is the congestive process ; there is a well-marked ulcer at one point, its base extending to the peritoneal coat, so that only the serous covering appears to intervene between the bowel lumen and the abdominal cavity. Both small and large bowel are congested, while they appear thinner than in health.

No. 2. Perhaps the most interesting pathological appearance is that presented by the duodenum. This part of the bowel is much congested, its vessels being greatly engorged ; two hæmorrhagic areas of

PLATE X.

- FIG. 17. Section of mucous membrane of upper bowel of healthy guinea-pig showing the normal appearance of the glands and villi, $\times 105$.
- FIG. 18. Section of mucous membrane of upper bowel of guinea-pig (No. 5) which died as a result of a crushed oats and autoclaved milk dietary, $\times 105$. Note: atrophy and degeneration of secretory elements. Compare with Fig. 17.
- FIG. 19. Section of upper bowel of guinea-pig (No. 3) which died as a result of a crushed oats and autoclaved milk dietary, $\times 105$. Note: degenerative changes in mucous membrane (M); extensive hæmorrhagic infiltration (H); diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration with segmentation and fragmentation of muscle fibres of myenteron (A). Compare with Fig. 3.
- FIG. 20. Section of upper bowel of guinea-pig (No. 4) which died as a result of a dietary of crushed oats and autoclaved milk, $\times 105$. Note: degenerative changes in mucous membrane (M) and diffuse hæmorrhagic infiltration of muscular coat (A). Segmentation and fragmentation of muscle fibres. Compare with Fig. 3.

Fig. 17.

Fig. 18.

Fig. 19.

Fig. 20.

extensive proportions almost surround the bowel circumference. On opening the duodenum, congestion of the mucous membrane was seen to be pronounced and numerous ecchymoses were scattered over its surface; the viscus was transparent at one part, the peritoneal coat alone appearing to intervene at this area between the bowel lumen and the abdominal cavity.

No. 3. The duodenum is much congested and turgid and its mucous membrane is studded with capillary hæmorrhages. The rest of the bowel is excessively thin.

No. 4. Apart from a moderate degree of generalized congestion of the bowels, and abnormal tenuity, no noteworthy macroscopical characters were recorded.

It appears then that congestive, hæmorrhagic, atrophic and necrotic changes in the bowel walls, usually most pronounced in the upper intestine, are common consequences in guinea-pigs of dietaries deficient in accessory food factors. It will have been noted that in both Aves and in guinea-pigs, the pathological processes are similar in character as well as in distribution. The relatively less frequent presence of these lesions in pigeons whose dietary was deficient in the 'B' factor only, the fact that pigeons deprived of both 'B' and 'C' factors suffered from pathological lesions of the bowel as pronounced as did those deprived of all three classes of accessory food factors, the fact that these lesions were equally well-marked in guinea-pigs subjected to complete 'vitaminic' starvation and in guinea-pigs deprived only of the 'C' factor, indicate that the congestive and hæmorrhagic lesions in the intestines of both species are largely, if not mainly, due to the absence of fresh green foods from the dietary. Control guinea-pigs fed on crushed oats, autoclaved milk and on abundance of fresh vegetables were wholly protected from gastro-intestinal lesions. It is worthy of comment that the functional perfection of the gastro-intestinal tract in herbivorous animals, appears to be dependent in considerable measure on accessory food factors found in fresh vegetable foods.

Having regard to the readiness with which accessory food factors of the 'C' class are destroyed in the process of cooking, their absence from the dietaries of human beings, or their long-continued sub-minimal supply, may have an important bearing on the genesis of gastro-intestinal disorders. These observations appear to provide

an explanation of the beneficial action of orange juice on the digestive and assimilative processes in bottle-fed infants.

Before leaving this subject, I would again direct attention to the fact that the intestinal lesions I have described in guinea-pigs were present in the majority of my cases before clinical evidences of scurvy were apparent. I suggest, therefore, that the symptoms of scurvy, as described in text-books, are the gross evidences of a disordered state of metabolism, the minor or pre-scorbutic manifestations of which are probably frequently overlooked, especially in children.

COMMENTARY.

Interpreted in terms of bowel function, the derangements to which such pathological changes as have been described may ultimately lead can be grouped as follows:—

- (1) Impairment of the neuro-muscular control of the bowel; impaired transport of the intestinal contents along the alimentary canal.
- (2) Impairment of assimilative power.
- (3) Impairment of secretory function.
- (4) Impaired protective resources leading to infection of the mucous membrane of the bowel by pathogenic saprophytes or ingested bacteria, and to systemic infection therefrom.

Unwilling as I am to apply too directly to the human subject the experimental results of intensive 'vitaminic' starvation as observed in birds and in guinea-pigs, we may, I think, regard the changes I have described as applicable in some degree to man.

It is my experience that, while complete deprivation of accessory food factors will cause the relatively rapid appearance of so-called 'polyneuritis'* in birds, sub-minimal provision of these substances, protracted over prolonged periods of time, will, especially in young and growing birds, eventually lead to a like morbid state. It is, I think, with sustained sub-minimal supply of accessory food factors that the physician is mainly

* The term 'polyneuritis', as applied to the morbid state resulting in pigeons from an exclusive dietary of autoclaved milled rice, is a misnomer. It suggests that the nervous tissues are exclusively or mainly involved in the pathological process, whereas in reality no organ or tissue escapes the consequences of 'vitaminic' deficiency; some, indeed, such as the reproductive organs, the spleen, the thymus, and the digestive organs, are more gravely affected than is the nervous system.—R. McC.

concerned in practice. Complete 'vitaminic' deprivation is, as I have pointed out in another place, relatively rare⁽⁴⁾; incomplete "vitaminic" deprivation—or sub-minimal supply of accessory food factors—is relatively frequent. If, in the light of the histo-pathological findings here recorded, we consider the case of children fed, it may be from birth, on foods deficient in these essential substances, and the frequency with which in later life their dietary continues to be ill-balanced and defective, we are, I venture to think, in a position to realize the ultimate consequences of such a dietary and to anticipate the sequence of events leading up to grave derangements of bowel function. Food deficiency also prepares the soil for bacterial growth and the resultant morbid states will vary with the nature of the organisms which may become implanted upon it. This knowledge, if it does not enable us to account fully for such gastro-intestinal disorders as mucous disease, celiac disease, and chronic intestinal stasis, will at least help us to a better understanding of their genesis.

I. MUCOUS DISEASE.

I have referred to the fact that pigeons fed on an exclusive dietary of autoclaved rice frequently suffer from diarrhoea⁽⁴⁾, and have pointed out that this symptom of 'vitaminic' deficiency can, in a proportion of cases, be made to disappear, often with surprising rapidity, by the administration of the alcoholic extracts of the yolks of eggs. Others have drawn attention to the almost constant occurrence of diarrhoea or of colitis as precursors or concomitants of the condition known as 'war oedema,' a malady proved to be due to food deficiency⁽⁵⁾. Clinical evidence of bowel derangements due to this cause are, therefore, not lacking. If, then, we attempt, from the results of our histo-pathological observations, to provide an explanation of the origin of mucous disease, we may, I think, surmise that continued sub-minimal 'vitaminic' supply will lead to that state of chronic gastro-intestinal catarrh which characterizes this disorder.

Mucous disease is very common amongst European children in India who are fed largely on sterilized milk (milk, which, in my own experience, is often poor in 'vitaminic' content), artificial foods, white bread, polished rice, poor butter, over-cooked vegetables and excessive quantities of sugar. Therapeutic experience of this malady shows how readily it yields to limitation of carbohydrates and to a rationaly-

balanced dietary of good 'vitaminic' quality. The mucous stools, the diarrhoea, the peevishness, the unhealthy appetite rapidly disappear on such a regimen, as also do the 'night terrors' from which the subjects of mucous disease so frequently suffer.

I do not wish to dogmatize with regard to the genesis of this malady. I would but draw attention to the fact that an ill-balanced diet, deficient in accessory food factors, is capable of giving rise in pigeons to a state of chronic congestion of the intestinal mucosa, often accompanied with hypertrophy of the adrenal glands; the relief afforded to children suffering from mucous disease by the correction of their ill-balanced dietaries may find an explanation in this fact.

II. COELIAC DISEASE.

One cannot read the illuminating account of this disorder given by Dr. G. F. Still⁽⁶⁾ in his recent Lumleian lectures without considering the possibility that it also may owe its origin to similar dietetic deficiencies. Its absence in breast-fed children, its onset between the age of nine months and two years, the diarrhoea which so frequently precedes it, the cessation of growth, the ill-formed pale 'oatmeal' stools, the frequent association of scorbutic symptoms, the abdominal distension, the afebrile nature of the malady, the diminished size of the liver, the blood changes, the occurrence of oedema, the thin bones, the muscular feebleness—all these find their counterpart in pigeons fed on an exclusive dietary of autoclaved milled rice⁽¹⁾. The pathological findings recorded in this paper indicate with what readiness pathogenic organisms may invade the atrophying intestinal mucous membrane and lead to inflammatory states and fibrotic thickenings therein. The enlargement of the adrenals, which is so constant a result of 'vitaminic' starvation, and so frequently associated with oedema in birds, may not be wanting in coeliac disease; I can find, in the literature available to me, no records with regard to the adrenals in this malady.

I venture to suggest that those who have the opportunity should examine their cases of coeliac disease, and more especially all available *post-mortem* material, from the point of view of food deficiency. Whether or not this malady is found to be due primarily to such deficiency, it would appear probable that a number of its characteristics are secondary to the imperfect assimilation of these essential ingredients of the food.

If, now, we consider the possibility of sub-minimal 'vitaminic' supply protracted over prolonged periods from childhood onwards, we have, I think, a new view-point from which to consider the genesis of that common disorder :

III. CHRONIC INTESTINAL STASIS.

In the recent edition of Sir Arbuthnot Lane's work on this subject(7), Professor Arthur Keith draws attention to two anatomical factors which he regards as of primary importance in the causation of chronic intestinal stasis : (1) Defective action on the part of the abdominal musculature, and (2) a lesion of the neuro-muscular system of the intestine.

The histo-pathological findings recorded in this paper indicate one means by which both the abdominal musculature and the neuro-muscular system of the intestine may be simultaneously impaired in functional capacity. Deficiency of certain accessory food factors leads to atrophy of all muscular tissue as well as to disordered function or actual degeneration of motor nerve cells throughout the entire body. The abdominal musculature and the nerve elements controlling it must of necessity suffer along with other muscular and nervous tissues. It may be concluded, then, that defective action on the part of the abdominal musculature will ultimately result in consequence of deficiency of accessory food factors.

In addition to this functional defect on the part of the abdominal wall, we find also in pigeons and in guinea-pigs starved of 'vitamines' unquestionable evidence in the wall of the intestine itself of neuro-muscular lesions of great significance. Whether or not we are justified in applying these findings to the genesis of stasis in the human subject, we may at least regard with suspicion human food which does not conform to standard in respect to perfect 'vitaminic' balance.

There can be no doubt that the dietaries of children amongst the poorer, and often amongst the richer, classes are frequently deficient in these important ingredients. Subsistence on such ill-balanced dietaries from childhood onwards may be regarded as calculated to lead to defect of the abdominal musculature, to neuro-muscular lesions of the intestine and to changes in the glandular elements of its mucous membrane. Indeed, the pathological changes in the large bowel in stasis, as described

by Professor Keith, are strikingly similar to those I have enumerated as occurring in pigeons fed on a 'vitamine'-free food. He describes the morbid changes as affecting two systems—the glandular and the neuro-muscular: 'The chief change in the muscular coats of the diseased great bowels removed from cases of enterostasis is a fibrosis—one which mainly affects the tissue between the outer and inner coats of the bowel, the intermediate stratum which insheathes the myenteric plexus. Degeneration in areas of the musculature, particularly of the outer longitudinal coat, also occurs. In every case there are inflammatory changes varying in degree. There are many marked changes in the lining glandular epithelium and in the submucous coat. One notes also that there is engorgement of the subperitoneal vessels, and that the subperitoneal tissue is much thicker and denser than is normal.' Having regard to the fact that the pathological processes I have described are acute in nature, and induced by intensive 'vitaminic' deprivation, whereas those recorded by Professor Keith are chronic, the similarity between them suggests that sub-minimal 'vitaminic' supply protracted from an early age has a fundamental influence in causing the lesions found in stasis. However this may be, we must regard with suspicion an influence which is capable of providing at once the anatomical conditions necessary for the development of stasis and the facilities for systemic infections which are known to result from it.

OBSERVATIONS ON THE EFFECTS OF 'VITAMINIC' SUBSTANCES AS CURATIVE AGENTS IN 'POLYNEURITIS GALLINARUM.'

In the course of the present research, many observations have been made with regard to the curative action of 'vitaminic' extracts, and also of such whole grains as *mung dal* in the morbid state induced in pigeons by an exclusive dietary of autoclaved rice. Since these therapeutic trials bring into prominence certain points of interest, the following illustration may be given:

Two young pigeons developed *polyneuritis gallinarum* in typical form and in severe degree as a result of an exclusive diet of autoclaved rice and butter. Both birds presented pronounced cerebellar symptoms and astasia; both had severe convulsive seizures turning 'cart-wheels' backwards at frequent intervals⁽¹⁾. At this stage, the birds were artificially fed with the *dry whole grains* of *mung dal* (a species of pea). Within twenty-four hours the convulsions had ceased, the cerebellar

symptoms had disappeared, and both birds were able to walk, although with a high-stepping and uncertain gait. They improved hourly on this dietary, both eating greedily of it. After the lapse of seventy-two hours one died suddenly. An autopsy was performed immediately; the whole gastro-intestinal tract was greatly engorged, the bowel walls were very thin and the upper four or five inches of the bowel distended with partly digested grain, the lower bowel being practically empty. It was noted that the contents of the upper bowel were not of that creamy consistency which is usual in health, but resembled rather a coarsely-ground collection of the ingested grain. The transport of the intestinal contents along the bowel lumen was delayed. Histological examination revealed pronounced changes in the bowel walls. The heart's blood yielded no growth by aërobic methods of culture.

The other bird survived. It was placed subsequently on mixed grains, and with the exception of a high-stepping and somewhat unsteady gait it exhibited after four days no symptoms referable to the nervous system. It appeared to be perfectly restored to health within ten days.

In connexion with this illustration I would direct attention to the following facts:

(1) The nervous symptoms present in *polyneuritis gallinarum* may be rapidly ameliorated, or even recovered from, and yet the bird die in consequence of gastro-intestinal lesions or (as I have found in other cases) of hæmic infections. This observation has, I think, a significant bearing on work designed to determine the 'vitaminic' value of food-stuffs by means of curative experiments in pigeons suffering from *polyneuritis gallinarum*.

(2) The rapid recovery from nervous symptoms indicates that the nervous system is, of all others, the least affected as regards organic lesions. In this system the symptoms are mainly the result of functional disorder. In the intestine, on the other hand, a greater destruction of tissue cells takes place. The intestinal lesions will consequently be recovered from more slowly.

(3) The remarkably rapid disappearance of convulsive seizures, of astasia and of cerebellar symptoms indicates that accessory food factors, if they do not actually activate or energize the nerve cells, at least they complete the circuit of nervous current. In their absence the large mass of nerve cells is incapable of normal activity; their provision establishes relatively normal cellular activity with dramatic suddenness.

Their action has been compared by Bayliss to that of catalytic substances; my own experimental experiences lead me to a like view.

(4) Solutions of 'vitaminic' substances (such for example as a solution in water of the dried alcoholic extract of the yolks of eggs) will, when administered to birds suffering from avian beri-beri, often cause recovery to take place with extraordinary rapidity. In cases, such as are recorded in the above illustration, recovery from nervous symptoms was quickly brought about by artificial feeding with the small Indian pea known as *mung dal*. The question then arises as to whether the liberation of accessory food factors from the dry hard seeds of *mung dal*, in quantity sufficient to bring about so rapid an amelioration of nervous symptoms, is wholly due to the ordered processes of digestion. It is hardly credible that a gastro-intestinal tract, in which are present the grave pathological changes I have described, could complete the processes of digestion with sufficient despatch to secure so rapidly beneficial a result. Indeed, in the bird which died digestion was far from complete, the bowel contents were abnormally delayed in transit and histological examination revealed an extreme degree of pathological change in the bowel walls. One is led to surmise, therefore, that some process more rapid than that of digestion may be concerned in the liberation of these substances—a process comparable, it may be, to the generation of growth ferments in seeds planted in warm moist earth.

CONCLUSIONS.

1. Dietaries deficient in accessory food factors give rise in pigeons and in guinea-pigs to congestive and atrophic changes in all coats of the bowel, to lesions of its neuro-muscular mechanism, to impairment of its digestive and assimilative functions, and to failure of its protective resources against infection.
2. The functional perfection of the gastro-intestinal tract is dependent in considerable measure on the adequate provision of accessory food factors derived from fresh fruit and vegetables.
3. Certain gastro-intestinal disorders in the human subject—of which three examples are referred to—may owe their origin to the long-continued sub-minimal supply of accessory food factors.

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